

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	PIT-STOP: Proton Irradiation Testing for Software compiler Protection
Project TA identifier	TA11-363
General application	Academic research on Software-Implemented Hardware Fault Tolerance (SIHFT). Targeting mainly space software (but not exclusively).
Type of test	SEE (mainly SEU but also SEFI and SEL)
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Date(s) of the experiment	2025-09-04, 2025-09-05
Facility	UMCG PARTREC
Amount of access granted	16h

Objectives of the experiments

The experiments were conducted to experimentally validate the ASPIS compiler-based SIHFT techniques under realistic radiation conditions. After earlier validation through laser-based fault injection and Cf-252 exposure performed at an ESA facility, the RADNEXT irradiation campaign aimed to obtain reliable SEU data by using a mono-energetic proton beam, chosen for its controlled flux and energy, its suitability for comparison with prior SIHFT studies, and its ability to induce faults without requiring device decapsulation. The selected Devices Under Test (DUTs) are COTS microcontrollers mounted on a custom board that allows automated monitoring and safe recovery. The DUTs were running real workloads during irradiation without timing interference from the instrumentation. Overall, the objective was to evaluate ASPIS across multiple software configurations and devices, identify areas for improvement, and provide experimentally grounded evidence to raise the technological readiness level of ASPIS and, more in general, of SIHFT technologies.

Experiment test report

Experimental setup

We exposed 4 identical DUTs (STM32F427) to the proton beam (2 DUTs at a time). The experimental setup can be seen in Figure 1, with two DUTs on the right-hand side, hit by the proton beam coming from the left-hand side of the picture. The disks in between are the degraders, necessary for tuning the beam energy at the DUT surface.

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Figure 1: The experimental setup showing the DUTs. Both microcontrollers are under the proton beam.

Initial testing campaign

The first campaign was focused on finding the best energy/flux value that can trigger a sufficient number of SEUs in the DUTs, avoiding SELs and SEFIs. The tested configurations and results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: SEU observed on a single DUT.

ID	Energy (MeV)	Flux (protons/cm ² /s)	Result
C1	50	10 ⁵	No SEUs observed
C3	75	10 ⁵	No SEUs observed
C4	100	10 ⁵	No SEUs observed
C5	100	10 ⁶	10 SEUs observed / 10 seconds
C6	100	10 ⁷	35 SEUs observed / 10 seconds
C10	100	10 ⁸	1631 SEUs / 60 seconds
C11	75	10 ⁸	1890 SEUs / 60 seconds
C12	50	10 ⁸	1579 SEUs / 60 seconds

SELs and SEFIs were never observed in this campaign. C11 was decided to be the candidate configuration as the number of SEUs was maximized.

SIHFT testing campaign (primary experiment)

For the main experiment, we used an energy of 75 MeV and a flux of 10⁸ protons/cm²/s (configuration C11).

The DUTs were running a full-fledged FreeRTOS system, running four concurrent real-time tasks:

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- Latnav: a lateral navigation benchmark that runs a PID controller to actuate ailerons, given a target coordinate.
- Airborne Collision Avoidance System (ACAS): an aerospace benchmark that emulates a collision avoidance system with a variable number of aircraft.
- Matrix Multiply (MM): a simple matrix multiplication benchmark.
- SHA: computes the cryptographic hash of a given input string.

The first DUT was flashed with the unprotected codebase, to establish an experimental baseline. The second DUT was flashed with the entire codebase, comprising the FreeRTOS kernel and all benchmarks, protected with ASPIS using sEDDI and RASM protection algorithms. In our setup, the motherboard was sending the DUTs a seed, which was used to compute the input parameters of each benchmark. The results of each individual job in the RTOS were used to compute a running CRC, which was sent to the MB at the end of a FreeRTOS hyperperiod for comparison against a golden CRC preliminarily computed. This way, the CRC coincides with the preliminarily computed if and only if both the system's logical and timing correctness are preserved.

At the end of each run, the result was classified according to standard terminology:

- *Masked*: The output of the run coincided with that of the golden run.
- *Silent Data Corruption (SDC)*: The output of the run did not match that of the golden run.
- *Detected*: One of the protection mechanisms of ASPIS detected the fault and called the corresponding fault handling routine.
- *Hard Fault*: The system triggered a fault handler, which may be due to several reasons: illegal memory access, illegal instruction, and so on.
- *Timeout*: The system was unresponsive and did not produce an output within the expected time boundary.

DUTs were power cycled after each run to ensure that no residual errors remained in the system.

The results are shown in Table 2 and Figure 2.

Table 2: Experimental results (% to the total number of executions)

Config	Masked	SDC	Hard Faults	Timeouts	Detected
Unprotected	98.342	0.433	0.780	0.444	N.A.
with ASPIS	97.188	0.092	0.845	0.277	1.597

Figure 2: Comparison factor for each experiment defined as $\text{outcome}_{\text{ASPIS}}/\text{outcome}_{\text{unprotected}}$.

These experimental results indicate that ASPIS reduces SDCs by a factor of nearly 5x, while slightly increasing the hard faults (which are less problematic than SDCs).

A few SELs have been observed during the long runs. All the 4 DUTs eventually suffered from a permanent fault on the programming interface and became impossible to re-flash.

Memory testing campaign (secondary experiment)

We have also performed a small sensitivity analysis to search for memory areas less or more sensitive than others. The configurations used were C6 and C11. We also collected data to observe if particular SEU patterns exist or if there's any difference between the sensitivity 0->1 and 1->0 of SEUs. The data from this campaign are still under evaluation.

DUT references and supporting equipment

DUTs:

- Manufacturer: STMicroelectronics
- Model: STM32F427VIT6TR
- Semiconductor technology: 90 nm
- Voltage: 3.3V (constantly monitored)

Supporting hardware:

- Custom "main" boards (SFERAv1) to control the experiment with PIC32MZ microcontrollers
- "SEL Destroyer" boards to remove power when SEL have been detected
- A Raspberry PI 4 and some laptops to gather data

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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